

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation report (acceptance note) for **TEBT-2024-0004**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	The Benefits of Preregistration and Registered Reports
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0004
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	2, plus Handling Editor
Submission Type	Expert Commentary ▾
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/dqap7
Status	Accepted ▾
Evaluation Date	30 Jun 2024
Evaluation Round	Peer-review round 1
Recommendation	Accept ▾
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	While a large number of revisions were recommended, they were generally about clarifying the argument being made rather than involving substantial changes to the central thesis of the article. In the opinion of the Handling Editor, the authors responded with comprehensive revisions that addressed all the points raised and the article can therefore be accepted for publication.

Acceptance note

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

The evaluators found this paper to be a wide-ranging review of the practice of preregistration, including the use of trial registries and the registered reports format for manuscripts, that should be a valuable resource for the toxicology and environmental health community. The article presents the issues around preregistration in an interesting light by looking in depth at definitions, constructs, misconceptions, potential risk and practices linked to the approach, and giving different points of view, meta-research results on the topic, and a useful set of citations across the article.

Recommendations for revisions made by the evaluators included placing more emphasis on storytelling, visualisation, and explanation of background terms to improve accessibility of the argument to a reader who can be expected to be unfamiliar with many of the issues being presented. They also suggested making the connection to the journal audience clearer and stronger early in the article. The authors made comprehensive revisions in response to these comments that significantly improved the accessibility and flow of their argument they present.

The response to comments from the evaluators also makes for interesting reading, and they are provided as supplemental materials to this report.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10985581](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10985581).